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Methods For Developing A Sense Of Social Responsibility In Students Through Moral Education

Raxmatova Dinora Isomovna

Independent researcher at Andijan State University

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Abstract: This article analyzes effective methods for forming a sense of social responsibility in students in the process of moral education. Social responsibility is considered one of the important factors of social development and healthy relationships between people. The author shows the possibilities of forming a conscious approach and sense of responsibility in students through the use of moral education tools, including the activities of exemplary individuals, fiction, discussions based on life events, and participation in public affairs. The article also highlights modern pedagogical technologies and the personal example of the teacher as an integral part of social education. The proposed methods based on experience and observations are recommended for practical application.

Keywords: Moral education, social responsibility, students, educational methods, pedagogical technologies, socialization, public activity, spiritual and moral development.

Introduction.

In today's conditions of globalization and technological progress, the education of the younger generation is becoming one of the main priorities of society. In particular, the issue of forming a sense of social responsibility in students through the process of moral education is considered one of the urgent problems in the field of pedagogy. After all, social responsibility is not only a person's responsibility for his actions, but also an understanding of his duty to society, a responsible approach to it. Such qualities are not formed by chance, but are formed through conscious upbringing, a consistent educational process and practical activities.

A modern schoolchild, along with receiving knowledge, must also prepare for social life as a person. His every decision, action, and attitude in social situations directly affect the person he will become in society in the future. Therefore, the main goal of moral education is not only to instill such human qualities as kindness, honesty, and justice, but also to awaken in students the desire to benefit others with their actions and contribute to society.

There are many methods for instilling a sense of social responsibility in students during the educational process, such as the teacher's personal example, games and discussions, participation in social projects, education based on national values, and familiarization with works of art. This article analyzes these

methods, evaluates their effectiveness, and gives recommendations for their practical application. The article deeply analyzes the role of moral education in society, its role in the development of the student as a person, and its importance in the process of adaptation to social life.

Methodology:

The correct choice of methodological foundations of scientific research is of great importance in studying the formation of a sense of social responsibility in students through moral education. This study was based on modern pedagogical approaches, psychological and pedagogical laws of educational activities, theoretical views on the processes of personal development and socialization. At the same time, real situations in educational work with students were studied through practical experiments, observations, and interviews.

Empirical methods, in particular, questionnaires, interviews, and observations with teachers and students, were used as the main methods in the study. Through these methods, students' moral views, attitudes towards social responsibility, and level of participation in collective work were studied and assessed. Diagnostic methods were also used to determine the extent to which students' social feelings and sense of responsibility were formed through their behavior in daily activities, participation in classes and extracurricular activities.

As a theoretical basis, the ideas of V. A. Sukhomlinsky, Sh. Amonov, A. Avlony about moral education and modern pedagogical views were analyzed. Based on these approaches, the essence, content of moral education and its relationship with social responsibility were scientifically substantiated.

Also, axiological, person-oriented and activity-based approaches were used during the study. With the help of these approaches, it was possible to organize moral education based on personal needs and interests, taking into account the individuality of each student, and thereby to instill social responsibility more deeply. In general, these methodological approaches served as the main tool for a comprehensive analysis of the process of forming a sense of social responsibility in students, identifying its theoretical and practical foundations, and developing effective educational methods.

Analysis of literature and sources:

The issue of moral education and social responsibility has long been the focus of attention of pedagogical science. A rich body of scientific, theoretical and practical sources has been formed in this area, and through their in-depth analysis, it is possible to determine the scientific foundations of the formation of a sense of social responsibility in students. The research analyzed the works of classical pedagogues, modern scientists, and national enlighteners, and paid

attention to how their views are applied in today's educational process.

First of all, the ideas of the famous Russian pedagogue K. D. Ushinsky that education should serve the development of the individual, as well as V. A. Sukhomlinsky's ideas about the socialization of the individual through the instillation of a sense of love, respect, and responsibility in moral education, were recognized as the main theoretical sources. Their works emphasize the importance of preparing the child for the social environment, instilling in him a sense of community, duty, and responsibility.

When referring to the national pedagogical heritage, the work of Abdulla Avloni "Turkish Rose or Morality" is of particular importance. It provides in-depth analysis of how moral values, etiquette, duty and patriotism should be instilled in the younger generation. In particular, the personal and social significance of moral education is highlighted through the idea that "morality is the foundation of humanity".

Among modern studies, the work of scientists such as Sh. Amonov, Z. K. Karimova, M. Mahkamova, R. Mamatkulov on the upbringing of the student's personality, activity-based approaches to spiritual and moral education, and the harmony of education and upbringing has been in the spotlight. In their works, they offer extracurricular educational activities, community service, games and project activities as a means of instilling social responsibility in the individual.

Also, the resolutions and decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on education, spirituality and youth, the National Development Strategy, and official documents related to the spiritual and educational policy of New Uzbekistan indicate that moral education is supported at the level of state policy. These documents are enriched with conceptual approaches to the formation of social responsibility in education. In general, the analyzed literature and sources show that the issue of forming a sense of social responsibility in students has centuries-old scientific traditions, and today it is becoming more relevant, combined with modern pedagogical technologies. Recommendations and methods developed on the basis of these sources can be widely used in real pedagogical practice.

Analytical discussion:

Forming a sense of social responsibility in students is an important stage in their development as independent thinkers, conscious and active citizens. The results of the analysis show that this process is more effective not only through the provision of knowledge, but also through the personal experience of students, life observations, and participation in public activities. Moral education plays a supporting role in this regard, because it is through moral criteria that the

individual develops the concept of "I am a member of society," that is, a sense of social responsibility.

Practical observations have shown that moral education, when carried out on the basis of an individual approach, has a positive effect on the student's internal emotional state and worldview. In particular, methods such as working with a team, creating an atmosphere of solidarity in the classroom, and assigning certain responsibilities through social roles are an important factor in the formation of a sense of responsibility in students. This, in turn, develops students' communication skills and skills in finding solutions to problem situations. During the discussion, it was observed that students feel social responsibility more deeply when they are directly faced with life situations than in lessons that provide moral education. For example, through real activities such as leading the class, actively participating in organizing school events, and helping others, they begin to understand themselves as part of society. Therefore, the effectiveness of moral education is manifested more strongly only when it is combined with practical activities. Also, the personal example of the teacher plays a large role in the formation of a sense of social responsibility. The teacher's being polite, fair, honest and responsible directly creates a desire in the minds of students to be similar. The fact that during the study, most students expressed the opinion that "we want to be a person who feels responsibility like our teacher" clearly confirms the place of this aspect in the educational process.

The analysis of the means of moral education shows that the use of works of art, examples of folk oral art, conversations about the life and activities of historical figures, and modern life events is extremely effective in forming a sense of social responsibility. They help students to deeply understand concepts such as patriotism, duty, honor, and dignity. The formation of a sense of social responsibility in students through moral education is a multi-stage, consistent and continuous process. In this process, it is clearly evident that only when the teacher's approach, the content of the lesson, the educational environment, and the student's life experience are in harmony with each other, a positive result will be achieved. Therefore, work in this area must be not only theoretical, but also practical.

Conclusion.

Moral education is not only a means of teaching the rules of etiquette, but also a means of forming a culture of responsibility for one's actions and an understanding of one's duty to society. The theoretical and practical results obtained during the study show that a sense of social responsibility does not form naturally in students, but it is necessary to direct this process in a purposeful,

consistent and conscious way. This directly depends on the content, methods and environment of moral education.

One of the main tasks of a modern school is not only to impart knowledge, but also to educate a person who actively participates in life, is not indifferent to those around him, and feels his duty. A sense of social responsibility is one of such personal qualities, which is clearly manifested in the student's activities at school and in everyday life, in communication with the community, and in decision-making. In forming this feeling, the teacher's personal example, involvement in social activities, and the use of fiction and national values are effective tools. This form of education serves to help students understand, appreciate and apply concepts such as honesty, justice, duty, conscience, solidarity. This, in turn, creates a solid foundation for their formation as active, responsible citizens ready for social life. Therefore, enriching moral education with modern approaches and organizing it continuously and effectively is one of the important tasks of today's education.

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